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clc;clear all;close all
%% 载入Homer2 预处理后的*.nirs文件，并对各个被试各个条件的 HRF 及可用
通道进行整理
%注意这个路径中只能包含预处理好的.nirs文件，不能包含预处理过程其他不同的
文件
datadir = 'C:nirs';
%使用dir 函数筛选在 datadir 路径下所有.nirs 格式的数据
dirinfo = dir(fullfile(datadir, '*.nirs'));
%提取数据的文件名信息
file_names = {dirinfo.name};
MeasListAct = [];

%导入第 subj 个被试的信息
for subj = 1:length(file_names)
    %读取.nirs文件
    load(strcat(datadir, '/',file_names{1,subj}),'-mat')
    badt = find(procResult.tIncAuto==0);
    procResult.dc(badt,:,:) = nan;
    %保存 procResult.dc 变量
    %procResult.dc 是 3D 数据：时间*类型(HBO,HBR,HBT)*通道
    alldc(:,:,:) = procResult.dc;
    alldc_all{subj,1} = alldc;
    %MeasListAct 存放所有被试通道好坏的信息 被试*通道
    MeasListAct(subj,:)=SD.MeasListAct(1:length(SD.MeasListAct)/2,1);
    clear alldc
end

%汇总每个被试有多少个通道是可用的
NumValidChannal = sum(MeasListAct,2);

for subj = 1:length(alldc_all)
    %找到被试的坏通道的序号 如果 subj 被试有坏通道，则 ind 中的值是具体的通
道编号
    %如果 subj 被试没有有坏通道，则 ind 为[]空
    ind = find(MeasListAct(subj,:)==0);
    %判断 ind 是不是不为空
    %如果 ind 不为空 即该被试有坏通道，则运行
    if ~isempty(ind)
        %将 alldc_all 中的所有时间所有类型所有坏的通道 该被试的数据替换为 NaN
        alldc_all{subj,1}(:, :, ind) = NaN;
    end
end
end

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save alldc_all.mat alldc_all
%% 提取 evt 和 mark 数据
clc;clear all
%同上，使用dir 函数筛选在 datadir 路径下所有.evt 格式的数据
datadir = 'C:nirs';
dirinfo = dir(fullfile(datadir, '*.evt'));
file_names = {dirinfo.name};

for subj = 1:length(file_names)
    %读取.evt文件
    mark=textread(strcat(datadir, '/',file_names{1,subj}));
    %保存每位被试的 mark 信息
    mark_all{subj,1} = mark;
    mark_all{subj,2} = file_names{subj};
    clear mark
end

%转换为相应的 mark 编号
for subj = 1:size(mark_all,1)
    for num = 1:size(mark_all{subj,1},1)
        a2 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,2);
        a3 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,3);
        a4 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,4);
        a5 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,5);
        a6 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,6);
        a7 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,7);
        a8 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,8);
        a9 = mark_all{subj,1}(num,9);
        a10 = a2 + a3*2 + a4*4 + a5*8 + a6*16 + a7*32 + a8*64 + a9*128 ;
        mark_all{subj,1}(num,10) = a10;
    end
end
clear a2 a3 a4 a5 a6 a7 a8 a9 a10
save mark_all.mat mark_all

%% 提取特定 HbO/Hb/HbT 数据
clc;clear all
load alldc_all.mat
for i = 1:length(alldc_all)
    %构造数据 提取 dc 的所有时间 第 1 个血氧浓度类型的 所有通道的数据
    %也可选择自己想要的通道时可以将最后一个冒号改为[] []里面放上自己想要的
    通道数 用空格或逗号隔开

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oxyData=fillnans(squeeze(alldc_all{i,1}{:,1,:}));
oxyData_all{i,1} = oxyData;
i
end
save oxyData_all.mat oxyData_all

%% 降采样
clc;clear all
load oxyData_all.mat
%将采样率由 7.8125Hz 降为 1Hz
for x=1:size(oxyData_all,1)
    datatemp= oxyData_all{x,1};
    time_length = floor(size(datatemp,1)/7.8125);
    for y = 1:time_length
        resampled_sub{x,:}(y,:) = mean(datatemp(floor(1
(y-1)*7.8125):round(y*7.8125),:),1);
    end
end

%将被试分开，为之后 wtc 做准备
for x = 1:2:size(resampled_sub,1)
    tempbuff1{x,1} = resampled_sub{x,1};
    tempbuff2{x,1} = resampled_sub{x+1,1};
end
tempbuff1(2:2:size(tempbuff1,1),:)=[];
tempbuff2(2:2:size(tempbuff2,1),:)=[];

save tempbuff1.mat tempbuff1
save tempbuff2.mat tempbuff2

%% wtc
clc;clear all
load tempbuff1.mat
load tempbuff2.mat
for x = 1:size(tempbuff1,1)
    for y = 1:size(tempbuff1{x,1},2)
        sub1 = tempbuff1{x,1}{:,y};
        sub2 = tempbuff2{x,1}{:,y};
        [Rsq{x,y},period{x,y},scale{x,y},coi{x,y},sig95{x,y}] = wtc(sub1,sub2,'mcc',0);
    end
end
end

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save allsub_wtc.mat Rsq period scale coi sig95
%Rsq(频率 X 时间):WTC 值; period:周期信息

%% 选择频段
clc;clear all
load allsub_wtc.mat
load mark_all.mat
%根据 mark 提取数据
%任务态 组块任务提取
for i = 1:size(Rsq,1)
    for k = 1:size(Rsq,2)
        for j = 1:size(mark_all{i,1},1)
            if mark_all{i,1}(j,10) ==4
                task1_data
                Rsq{i,k}(:,floor(mark_all{i,1}(j,1)/7.8125):floor(mark_all{i,1}(j+1,1)/7.8125));
                task1_data_all{i,k} = task1_data;
            end
        end
    end
end
%静息态 组块任务提取
for i = 1:size(Rsq,1)
    for k = 1:size(Rsq,2)
        for j = 1:size(mark_all{i,1},1)
            if mark_all{i,1}(j,10) ==1
                rest_data
                Rsq{i,k}(:,floor(mark_all{i,1}(j,1)/7.8125):floor(mark_all{i,1}(j+1,1)/7.8125));
                rest_data_all{i,k} = rest_data;
            end
        end
    end
end

%消掉时间维度
%然后叠加平均
%task1
me1 = [];
for x = 1:size(task1_data_all,1)
    for y = 1:size(task1_data_all,2)
        me1 = mean(task1_data_all{x,y}(1:23,:),2); %23 是被试对数
        task1_data_all_all{x,y} = me1;
    end
end
end

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%rest
me2 = [];
for x = 1:size(rest_data_all,1)
    for y = 1:size(rest_data_all,2)
        me2 = mean(rest_data_all{x,y}(1:23,:),2);
        rest_data_all_all{x,y} = me2;
    end
end
% 将任务态与静息态做配对样本 t 检验
for y= 1:size(task1_data_all_all,2)
    for x= 1:size(task1_data_all_all,1)
        for k = 1:size(task1_data_all_all{x,y},1)
            data_ttest{y,k}(x,1) = task1_data_all_all{x,y}(k);
            data_ttest{y,k}(x,2) = rest_data_all_all{x,y}(k);
        end
    end
end

for x = 1:size(data_ttest,1)
    for y = 1:size(data_ttest,2)
        [h,p,ci,stats] = ttest(data_ttest{x,y}(:,1),data_ttest{x,y}(:,2));
        p_value(x,y) = p;
        t_value(x,y) = stats.tstat;
    end
end
figure(1)
imagesc(t_value);
figure(2)
imagesc(p_value);
p_loca = p_value<.05;
figure(3)
imagesc(p_loca);
%% 确定频段以后 做分析

clc;clear all
load allsub_wtc.mat
load mark_all.mat
pd1 = 5;
pd2 = 28;

%根据 mark 提取数据
%任务态 组块任务提取

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for i = 1:size(Rsq,1)
    for k = 1:size(Rsq,2)
        for j = 1:size(mark_all{i,1},1)
            if mark_all{i,1}(j,10) ==4
                task1_data =
Rsq{i,k}(pd1:pd2,floor(mark_all{i,1}(j,1)/7.8125):floor(mark_all{i,1}(j+1,1)/7.8125))
;
                task1_data_all{i,k} = task1_data;
            end
        end
    end
end

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%静息态 组块任务提取

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for i = 1:size(Rsq,1)
    for k = 1:size(Rsq,2)
        for j = 1:size(mark_all{i,1},1)
            if mark_all{i,1}(j,10) ==1
                rest_data =
Rsq{i,k}(pd1:pd2,floor(mark_all{i,1}(j,1)/7.8125):floor(mark_all{i,1}(j+1,1)/7.8125))
;
                rest_data_all{i,k} = rest_data;
            end
        end
    end
end

```

%消掉频率&时间维度

%然后叠加平均

%task1

me1 = [];

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for x = 1:size(task1_data_all,1)
    for y = 1:size(task1_data_all,2)
        me1 = mean(mean(task1_data_all{x,y},2));
        task1_data_all_all(x,y) = me1;
    end
end

```

end

% ...

%rest

me2 = [];

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for x = 1:size(rest_data_all,1)
    for y = 1:size(rest_data_all,2)
        me2 = mean(mean(rest_data_all{x,y},2));
        rest_data_all_all(x,y) = me2;
    end
end

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end
%Z 转换
for x = 1:size(task1_data_all_all,1)
    for y = 1:size(task1_data_all_all,2)
        r = task1_data_all_all(x,y);
        r_new = atanh(r);
        task1_data_all_all_z(x,y) = r_new;
    end
end
for x = 1:size(rest_data_all_all,1)
    for y = 1:size(rest_data_all_all,2)
        r = rest_data_all_all(x,y);
        r_new = atanh(r);
        rest_data_all_all_z(x,y) = r_new;
    end
end

% 将任务态与静息态做配对样本 t 检验
for x = 1:size(task1_data_all_all_z,2)
    [h,p1,ci,stats] = ttest(task1_data_all_all_z(:,x),rest_data_all_all_z(:,x));
    p_value(1,x) = p;
    t_value(1,x) = stats.tstat;
end
%FDR 矫正
p_fdr1 = mafdr(p1_value, 'BHFDR', true);

for x = 1:size(task1_data_all_all_z,2)
    [h,p2,ci,stats] = ttest(task2_data_all_all_z(:,x),rest_data_all_all_z(:,x));
    p_value(1,x) = p;
    t_value(1,x) = stats.tstat;
end
%FDR 矫正
p_fdr2 = mafdr(p2_value, 'BHFDR', true);

[h,p3,ci,stats] =
ttest2(Lecture_teaching_task1_data_all_all_z,Body_teaching_task1_data_all_all_z);
p_fdr3= mafdr(p3, 'BHFDR', true);
[h,p4,ci,stats] =
ttest2(Lecture_teaching_task2_data_all_all_z,Body_teaching_task2_data_all_all_z);
p_fdr4= mafdr(p4, 'BHFDR', true);

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